

MUSIC PERFORMANCE AND SOCIAL REALITY: FELA KUTI'S *ZOMBIE* AND 2FACE IDIBIA'S *E BE LIKE SAY AS* PARADIGM.

Oja Paul EGWEMI¹, Salifu MUSA²

¹Department of Theatre Arts,
Kogi State University, Anyigba, Nigeria
e-mail: Egwemi.op@ksu.edu.ng.

²Department of Theatre Arts,
Kogi State University, Anyigba, Nigeria
e-mail: mcdegreat@gmail.com

Abstract

Nigeria for many decades has been bedeviled with antisocial problems such as corruption and nepotism leading to social vices like terrorism, kidnapping, armed robbery and many others. These social vices have in one way or the other thwarted the socioeconomic and political life of the nation. The study adopts critical discourse analysis methodology through which it analyzes the philosophy and thematic preoccupation of Fela Kuti's *Zombie* and 2Face Idibia's *E Be Like Say* in relations to the Nigerian social realities. The result shows that music performance in Nigeria has over the years been designed to lampoon some of the social ills facing the nation. The paper concludes that music performance like other art forms can be channeled to counter antisocial problems in the country for national development.

Introduction

It's not an over statement to say that Nigerian book of history is rich in violent events ranging from civil war, tribal and political motivated terrorism and host of others. At the moment, the rate of crime wave in the country is on the increase. Cases of armed robbery attacks, kidnapping, farmers and herdsman clashes and lots more are heard always across the country. The reason for this is not hard to explain. It is because the country is built on the foundation of socio-political ills such as corruption, dictatorship, oppression, nepotism and prejudice. Amirikpa states that:

“The Nigerian nation has been riddled by myriad of problems that range from ethnicity, religious bigotry, paucity of progressive national leadership, monumental systemic corruption that have thwarted the evolution of genuine nation state.... (92).

These situations are some of the social realities confronting the Nigerian nation. And these social problems have in no little measure affected the socio-economic and political growth of the country. A number of strategies have been engaged by Nigerians and Nigeria government to address these issues for national transformation. One of these strategies is music. The roles of music in social control can never be over mentioned. Music are invariably products of the happenings in the society while the artist (musician) retails his/her role as the conscience of his/her society. Over the years, music has been used by many Nigerian musical artists to educate Nigerians about their social realities for positive change and development. In Nigerian history, we have witnessed the significant roles played by musicians in the development of Nigeria. Artistes of yester-years like Dr. Victor Abimbola Olaiya, I.K. Dairo, Dennis Osadebey, Bongos Ikuue and a host of others contributed in mobilizing a Nigerian society towards an awareness and appreciation of the nation's transformation from the colonial independent status. (Adaba, 14) During the Nigerian civil war of 1967-70, songs were composed to boost the morale of the troops at the war front. Artist (musician) like Dan Maraya of Jos, was at a point sent to the war front to entertain the troops. Music was used to mobilize the masses during this period for the purpose of unity, construction, rehabilitation and reconstruction. Music and musicians have helped over the ages and are still contributing to the building of the Nigerian society. This paper consequently discusses the concept of music performance and social realities in Nigerian society using Fela Kuti's *Zombie* and 2face Idibia's *E Be Like Say* as paradigm.

Theoretical Framework

This paper adopts conflict theory as its theoretical framework. Conflict theory is a dialectical method of analysis. It is a critical stance toward existing social arrangements and political program of revolution or reform. Wright Mills has been referred to as the founder of modern conflict theory. In Mills' view:

Social structures are created through conflict between people with different interests. Individuals and resources, in turn, are influenced by these structures and by the unequal distributions of power and resources in the society. The power elites like the military emerged from the fusion of the corporate elite, the pentagon, and the executive branch of government. The interests of these elites are opposed to those of the people. The policies of the power elite would result in increased

escalation of conflict, production of weapons of mass destruction and possibly the annihilation of human race. (16)

Another theorist considered as one of the founders of modern conflict theory is Gene Sharp. Power is not monolithic, that is, it does not derive from some intrinsic quality of those who are in power. The power of any state regardless of its particular organization—ultimately derived from the subjects of the state. The fundamental belief is that any power structure relies upon the subject obedience to the orders of the ruler or rulers. If subject do not obey, leaders have no power. (Sharp, 102)

This theory is important for the study because the paper is weaved around the importance of music in relation to social realities in Nigerian society. Therefore, it should be noted that there is the ever-existing inter-dependence between the artist and his immediate society for the art to meaningfully thrive in dealing with the home, the society, the times, philosophical, historical, religion and political issues. The theory argues for well-being of the masses by placing them at the centre of any governmental policy. Fela's *Zombie* was waxed in 1976 and deals with the repressive military regime which demand people only to take orders and not ask questions. Thereby reducing man to an animated corpse. Like Fela, 2face Idibia's *E Be Like Say* expresses the hostile attitude of the political class against the masses who are forced into living in abject poverty after their common wealth has been stolen. The two artistes are consciously chosen to recognize that as long as music is tied to the happenings in the society, it retains its utilitarian values.

Place of Music in the Society

Music is important in every aspects of Nigerian society. The first and fundamental role of music is entertainment. Music delights and entertains the people. Apart from entertainment, the place of music is also seen in the social and cultural life of the people. No cultural and social ceremonies like festivals, religious rites, marriage ceremonies and host of others are carried out in Nigeria without the use of music. It is in line with this that Bode Omojola posits that: "... Musical performance in Nigeria maintains an integral relationship with other aspects of the peoples' cultural traditions from which much of the character of music and its conception by the people often derive". (43)

Most importantly, music is used to express and discuss social issues bothering the nation. Music in this context plays the role of social control. It assists to improve Nigerian social system.

It lampoons social ills such as corruption, tyranny, oppression, nepotism and ethnicity. It exposes Nigerian social menace, condemns them and suggests a way forward. Music of the Nigerian popular musical artists like Fela Kuti, 2face Idibia and the host of others have over the years served the nation in this capacity.

Biography of the Selected Artists: Fela Kuti and 2face Idibia

Fela Kuti: Fela Anikulapo Kuti (1938-1997) was a Nigerian multi-instrumentalist, musician, composer, pioneer of the Afrobeat music genre and human right activist. Fela was sent to London in 1958 to study medicine but decided to study music instead at Trinity College of Music, the trumpet being his preferred instrument. While there, he formed the band Koola Lobitos, playing a fusion of Jazz and highlife. In 1963, Fela moved back to newly Independent Federation of Nigeria, and trained as a radio producer for the Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation. In 1967, he went to Ghana to think up a new musical direction. That was when he first called his music Afrobeat. Kuti's music was popular among the Nigerian public and Africans in general. He made the decision to sing in Pidgin English so that his music could be enjoyed by individuals all over Africa where the local languages spoken are very diverse and numerous. In 1970, Fela formed the Kalakuta Republic. This was when his lyrical theme changed from love to social issues. He was referred to as one of African's most challenging music performers. Fela released many albums that attacked social and political realities in Nigeria and Africa in general. Among his albums are *Alu Joh Jonki Joh*, *Lady*, *Gentleman*, *Shakara*, *Yellow Fever*, *Alagbon Close*, *Expensive shit Authority*, *Stealing and ITT*, and *Zombie*.

2face Idibia: Innocent Idibia (2face Idibia) was born in Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria. He is from Idoma ethnic group of the country. He attended Mount Saint Gabriel's Secondary School, Makurdi, Benue State. He enrolled at Institute of Management and Technology (IMT) Enugu, where he did his preliminary National Diploma course in Business Administration and Management, but he eventually dropped out to pursue his musical career. 2face has performed and produced many musical albums with lyrical themes ranging from love, philosophy of life, bad governance and many others. One of such music performances is *E Be Like Say*.

Analysis of the Selected Works: *Zombie* and *E Be Like Say*

Zombie and *E Be Like Say* are musical albums or performances with lyrical themes that discuss some of the social and political realities at different stages of the Nigerian history. *Zombie* is satirical piece of the Nigerian social realities within the nation's military regimes, 1966 – 1999.

The army held power in Nigeria without interruption apart from a short-lived return to democracy from 1979 – 1983. The military era was characterized by non-tolerance to criticism, dictatorship, corruption and violation of human rights. It has been observed that the wrong economic policy of the Nigerian military regimes was what led to the beginning of issues like high rate of poverty, child abuse, disease, institutional decay and urban dislocation. One of the evidences of this argument lies in the fact that the Nigerian traditional agricultural based economy was abandoned during the Nigerian military eras and the country became extremely dependent on exports of oil which due to frequent fluctuations in oil prices led to an unstable economy. The military rule in Nigeria without doubt was marked by economic collapse, dictatorship, political repression and systematic human rights violation. The national infrastructures and virtually all public institutions including the judiciary and the security forces decayed during this period.

Kuti's *Zombie* is a reflection of these situations. It discusses the behaviours of the Nigerian military leaders and that of their instruments of oppression and dictatorship who were the army officers. In other words, the music was a serious attack on Nigerian soldiers. Kuti uses the metaphor of the *Zombie* to describe the methods of the Nigerian military. At the time, the Nigerian soldiers were people of no rectitude and ethics. Their superiors used them to carry out all forms of human abuses. Like *Zombie*, people with extreme mental exhaustion, all their actions were regulated within the limit of their superiors' cruel orders. As Fela puts in the song:

Zombie O Zombie x2

Zombie no go go unless you tell am to go (Zombie)

Zombie no go stop unless you tell am to stop (Zombie)

Zombie no go turn unless you tell am to turn (Zombie)

Zombie no go think unless you tell am to think (Zombie)

Zombie O Zombie x2

That was the situation of the Nigerian army during the military regimes. There were many reports of series of abuses by the forces across the country. Members of the nation's armed forces unleashed terrors on the civilians in line with the tyrannical orders of their superiors without any sense of moral and ethical principles as Fela further describes them thus:

Go and kill (joro jara joro)

Go and die (joro jara joro)

Go an quench (joro jara joro)

Kuti's *Zombie* therefore, is a figuration of the soldiers who obey their leaders without arguments. Their leaders used them to cause all forms of atrocities during the repressive and dictatorship military regimes in the country. Music performs their utilitarian functions in their immediate society. *Zombie* falls under topics of protest and satire. *Zombie* is Kuti's creation to document dictatorship and brutality of the common men who were silenced in the face of massive looting during the Nigerian military regime.

2face Idibia's *E Be Like Say* on the other hand, exposes the level of corruption during the nation's democratic dispensation. Since the army returned power to the democratic government in 1999, the nation has witnessed many forms of corrupt practices leading to abject poverty and general decadence of the nation's economic and political systems. A situation where the politicians manipulate the consciousness and will of the people through 'god-fatherism' and other strategies in order to get hold of power and once they get there they abandon the poor masses to wallow in poverty. Each time they are in need of the same people during elections, they will approach them with little items and sugar-coated empty promises as 2face Idibia captures in his music thus:

Looking back through all the years
That you and I have spent together
It seems like you been playing me all the while
So many times, you asked me to put the whole of my trust in you
So many times you betrayed me and played me for a fool...

Like it has been earlier observed, Nigerian politicians normally use many strategies to get hold of power, and once they achieve their aims, they will abandon the electorates, who vote for them. They will regard their victory as a product of the money they spent during the election. This situation has for many decades enriched the nation with socio-political and economic problems such as poverty, poor health issues and insecurity as the vocalist further laments thus:

They don't really care about us
Because all they want to do is to get in touch with big bucks
Because they think that the money gives them the power
But the power is nothing
If your people cannot get quality education
The power is nothing
If your people keep dying of disease and starvation

The power is nothing

If your people have no peace

The power is nothing if your people cannot live in unity...

The social issues captured in Kuti's *Zombie* and 2face's *E Be Like Say* are some of the social realities facing Nigeria since the nation got her independence in 1960. It is therefore, important to note that these social realities and their effects on the nation can be best analysed with conflict theory. The conflict theory centres on the concept of social inequality in the division of resources and the conflict that exist between classes. Throughout the military government and present democratic regime in Nigeria, like it has been reflected in the selected musical pieces, the bourgeoisies who hold the nation's wealth and power have subjected the proletariats to harsh conditions. Marx posits that as the working class and the poor are subjected to worsening conditions, a collective consciousness would bring the inequality to light and potentially result in revolt. This is the situation in Nigeria since the nation got her independence in 1960. Several forms of violent and criminal scenes are seen across the country due to bad governance. It has been observed that the current security challenges facing the nation are products of the poor masses' revolt against the government for her incredibility and corrupt practices which has for many decades enriched the nation with unemployment, poverty and general collapse of the economy.

Conclusion/Recommendations

This paper has in a way attempted to show the relevance of music performance in the society. Musical artists examine their society and reflect the socio-cultural, political and economic problems bothering the society in their works with the sole aim of making a positive change. Fela Kuti's *Zombie* and 2face Idibia's *E Be Like Say* portray Nigerian social realities such as corruption and dictatorship. Kuti and Idibia have used their music to contribute to the building of the Nigerian society by direct participation through their art. They try to conscientize the masses about the corrupt nature of both the military and civilian regimes. Like Fela once said:

I am an artist. I have my reasons for being sad. I want to change sadness. I want people to be happy. And I can do it by playing happy music. And through music I tell them about the sadness of others... with my music I create change. I am using my music as a weapon... (127)

It is therefore, evident from the above, that the artist (musician) does not only satisfy the people around him by entertaining them, but also through music, informs the society, appeals to their conscience, mobilizes, educates and builds them.

References

- Abert, Oikolome. Stylistic Analysis of Afrobeat Music of Fela Anikulapo Kuti (PDF). Analysisworldmusic.com. retrieved, 2013.
- Amirikpa, O. Theatre and Challenges of Development in Nigeria. Ibadan: Constellation Books, 2016.
- Bordowiz, Hank. Noise of the World: Non-Western Musicians in their Own Worlds. Canada: Solt Skull Press, 2004.
- Durkheim, E. The Rules of Sociological Method. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1938.
- Marx and Engels. The Communist Manifesto, Introduction by Martin Malia. New York: Penguin Group, 1998.
- Ogunnaike, Lola. Celebrating the Life and Impact of the Nigerian Music Legend, Fela. New York: The New York Times, 2010.
- Omojola, Bode. "Linguistic and Musical Discourse in Modern Nigerian Music: A Study of the Choral Works of Okechukwu Ndubuisi (1939 – 1996)". In The Performer: Ilorin Journal of the Performing Arts. Department of the Performing Arts, University of Ilorin. Ilorin: 1999.
- Patt, Ray. Rhythm and Resistance: Explorations in Political Uses of Popular Music: Praeger, 1990.
- Tom, Adaba. "The Musician As Social Reformer". In Nigerian TheCom Review, Journal of Theatre and Communication. Jos, Vol. 1 No. 1 Nov,